

EFFECT OF YOGIC PRACTICES WITH AND WITHOUT DEEP RELAXATION TECHNIQUE ON STRESS AMONG SCHOOL GIRLS

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study was to find out the effect of yogic practices with and without deep relaxation technique on stress of school girls. To achieve the purpose of this study, forty five school girls studying in and around Kanchipuram District, Tamil Nadu, India were selected as subjects and they were divided into three equal groups of fifteen each. Group I underwent yogic practices with deep relaxation technique, Group II underwent yogic practices without deep relaxation technique and Group III acted as control. Group I and Group II underwent their respective training programmes for three days per week for twelve weeks and Group III acted as control in which they didn't undergo any special training programme apart from their daily curricular activities. The selected subjects were tested on the selected criterion variable namely stress at prior and immediately after the training programme. The analysis of covariance was used to find out the significant differences, if any, at prior and immediately after the training programme among groups on stress. Whenever the obtained 'F' ratio for adjusted post test was found to be significant, the Scheffe's test was applied as post hoc test to determine the paired men differences, if any. The level of confidence was fixed at .05 level which was considered as an appropriate.

Key Words: Yogic Practices With and Without Deepa Relaxation Technique, Stress, School Girls

Introduction:

The origin of yoga lies in antiquity. It was first expounded in the great shastras (texts), known as the Vedas. Four in numbers, these are the earliest scriptures known to mankind, extending back thousands of years. Vedas. Together, these texts explain and regulate every aspect of life, from supreme reality to all worldly affairs. Here, and in much classical literature to follow, is where one can see evidence of the origin of yoga.

The exact birth of the Vedas is lost in the distant past. The Vedas themselves were ancient hymns, originally sung in the forests by Rishis (seers) who lived remote, ascetic live sand in this way were passed from guru to disciple for perhaps thousands of years before being put to writing, Hindu tradition itself puts the Vedas as far back as 10,000 years. The origin of yoga can be traced back to the very oldest of these scriptures, the rig veda, which speaks about 'yoking the mind' to the 'highest truth'. But within these hymns from this ancient vedic period, one even see the actual word 'yoga' used occasionally as well. As Dr. Kumar Kaul says in his book, "Yoga in the Hindu Scriptures":

"All the four Vedic Samhitas refer directly or indirectly to the yoga system and the yoga traditions. In the first three Samhitas there are direct as well as indirect references to Yoga. But the atharavaveda gives the clear conception of Yoga describing the eight mystical circles (Chakras) and the nine gates of the human body - the golden sheath and the mystical wheel containing the thousand spokes. Therefore, it may be held that the Vedic seers and sages were aware of the nature, importance and implication of the practical aspects of Yoga." More Classical Literature like Bhagavadgita, Mahabharata, Ramayana, Upanishads, also Reveals the Origin of Yoga. Although it wasn't until recently when yoga earned massive recognition and gained a huge following, it has existed for the past thousands of years. The earliest written scriptures that would help trace the origins of yoga were found in the Indus Valley during an archaeological excavation. Hence, it could be very well that yoga started out during this early antique period.

Yoga also been associated by many to Stone Age Shamanism, although there is no valid link between the two except for the fact that having a few similarities in their method and approach. However, most modern yoga methods are still deeply rooted to the Indian philosophy, which provides this practice with its religious and spiritual aspect. Life can be stressful. For starters, there's your busy schedule - waking up super early for school, studying late at night for tests, juggling sports practice, homework, and meals. Everyday issues can add emotional stress, too - counseling a friend through a breakup, regretting a disagreement with a parent, weighing an important decision, or stressing over whether you'll make final cuts for the varsity team. With lots on your mind, it's easy to feel stressed.

There are many ways to cope with stress. Talking with friends, exercising, and seeing a school counselor are just a few. Yoga can help reduce stress because it promotes relaxation, which is the natural opposite of stress. Yoga can benefit three aspects of ourselves that are often affected by stress: our body, mind, and breathing.

Methodology:

The purpose of this study was to find out the effect of yogic practices with and without deep relaxation technique on stress of school girls. To achieve the purpose of this study, forty five school girls studying in and around Kanchipuram District, Tamil Nadu, India were selected as subjects and they were divided into three equal groups of fifteen each. Group I underwent yogic practices with deep relaxation technique, Group II underwent yogic practices without deep relaxation technique and Group III acted as control. Group I and Group II underwent their respective training programmes for three days per week for twelve weeks and Group III acted as control in which they didn't undergo any special training programme apart from their daily curricular activities. Stress was selected as criterion variable. All the subjects of three groups were tested on stress at prior to and immediately after the training programme. The analysis of covariance was used to analyze the significant difference, if any among the groups. The .05 level of confidence was fixed as the level of significance to test the "F" ratio obtained by the analysis of covariance, which was considered appropriate. The Scheffe's test was applied as post hoc test to find out the paired mean difference, if any,

Training Programme:

For yogic practices with deep relaxation technique group and yogic practices without deep relaxation technique group underwent their respective training programme for twelve weeks for three days per week. Training was given in the morning session. The training session includes warming up and limbering down. Every day the workout lasted for 45 to 60 minutes approximately. The subjects underwent their respective training programmes as per the schedules under the strict supervision of the investigator. During experimental period control group did not participate in any of the special training.

Analysis of the Data:

The influence of yogic practices with deep relaxation technique and yogic practices without deep relaxation technique on stress was analysed separately and presented below. The analysis of covariance on stress of the pre and post test scores of yogic practices with deep relaxation technique group and yogic practices without deep relaxation technique group and control group have been analyzed and presented in table 1.

Table 1: Analysis of Covariance of the Data on Stress of Pre and Post Tests Scores of Yogic Practices with Deep Relaxation Technique, Yogic Practices Without Deep Relaxation Technique and Control Groups

Test	Yogic Practices With Deep Relaxation Technique Group	Yogic Practices Without Deep Relaxation Technique Group	Control Group	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	Obtained 'F' Ratio
Pre Test								
Mean	57.73	56.80	54.93	Between	60.98	2	30.489	1.04
S.D.	1.18	1.26	1.19	Within	1232.27	42	29.34	
Post Test								
Mean	47.13	47.87	52.87	Between	292.04	2	146.02	4.53*
S.D.	1.21	1.09	1.35	Within	1353.20	42	32.22	
Adjusted Post Test								
Mean	46.05	47.60	54.22	Between	539.84	2	269.92	26.64*
				Within	415.396	41	10.13	

* Significant at .05 level of confidence.

(The table values required for significance at .05 level of confidence for 2 and 42 and 2 and 41 are 3.222 and 3.226 respectively).

The table 1 shows that the adjusted post-test means of yogic practices with deep relaxation technique group, yogic practices without deep relaxation technique group and control group on stress are 46.05, 47.60 and 54.22 respectively. The obtained "F" ratio of 26.64 for adjusted post-test means is greater than the table value of 3.226 for df 2 and 41 required for significance at .05 level of confidence on stress.

The results of the study indicated that there was a significant difference between the adjusted post-test means of yogic practices with deep relaxation technique group, yogic practices without deep relaxation technique group and control group on stress.

Since, three groups were compared, whenever the obtained 'F' ratio for adjusted post test was found to be significant, the Scheffe's test to find out the paired mean differences and it was presented in table 2.

Table 2: The Scheffe's Test for the Differences between Paired Means on Stress

Yogic Practices With Deep Relaxation Technique Group	Yogic Practices Without Deep Relaxation Technique Group	Control Group	Mean Differences	Confidence Interval Value
46.05	47.60	-	1.55*	1.49
46.05	-	54.22	8.18*	1.49
-	47.60	54.22	6.63*	1.49

* Significant at .05 level of confidence.

The table 2 shows that the mean difference values between yogic practices with deep relaxation technique group and yogic practices without deep relaxation technique group, yogic practices with deep

relaxation technique group and control group and yogic practices without deep relaxation technique group and control group 1.55, 8.18 and 6.63 respectively on stress which were greater than the required confidence interval value 1.49 for significance.

The results of this study showed that there was a significant difference between yogic practices with deep relaxation technique group and yogic practices without deep relaxation technique group, yogic practices with deep relaxation technique group and control group and yogic practices without deep relaxation technique group and control group on stress.

Results:

- There was a significant difference among yogic practices with deep relaxation technique group and yogic practices without deep relaxation technique group and control group on stress.
- There was a significant reduction in stress due to yogic practices with deep relaxation technique and yogic practices without deep relaxation technique.

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